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When opening the cardboard

We all know from our personal experiences that humans display a wide variety of emotions, both in response to their social interactions and in response to their material environment. These emotional responses can vary from the quiet satisfaction of completing a relative mundane task to the consuming frustration when things don't work out the way we planned. In psychology, it is also commonly accepted that emotion is one of the most central and pervasive aspects of human experience (e.g., Ackerman 1990, Davidson and Cacioppo 1992).

What we also know from our own experiences is that consumer products can be powerful emotional stimuli. Products can elicit a wide variety of emotions, both pleasant and unpleasant, strong and mild, simple and complex. This variety in emotional responses can be illustrated with some examples. Imagine the feeling of joy and expectation when opening the cardboard that contains one's very first own radio. Or imagine the feeling of pure frustration because of the stubbornly malfunctioning computer. And imagine the feeling of pride elicited by one's bright new sportscar, or the jealous responses of the happy new car owner's neighbours.

These examples illustrate not only the wide variety of emotions that products are able to elicit, but also that emotions are often not merely elicited by the product 'as such'. When a product elicits an emotion, it is always induced by a specific product-subject relationship and within a specific context. In our examples, a few years after first opening the cardboard, the same radio will probably elicit quite different emotions (the context has changed). Similarly, both the sportscar owner and his neighbour are responding to the same product, but with a different emotion (their relationships with the product differ).

Another complicating aspect of emotions is that they are personal. Even within the same context and product-subject relationship, two persons can still experience different emotional reactions towards a product. For example, when first confronted with the new Volkswagen Beetle, some people have positive responses whereas other people respond negatively. Moreover, in some cases products elicit combinations of different emotions within subjects as well. The emotional response of an individual to the Ford Ka

for example, could be mixed. Although on the one hand she doesn't like the design and therefore feels aversive, on the other hand she is inspired by the fact that the design has a distinct innovative quality. In this situation she experiences a mixture of both positive emotions, related to the innovative aspects, and negative emotions, related to the aesthetic aspects of the design.

How is it possible that -regardless of the context- products elicit such 'mixed emotions', combinations of different emotions at the same time, both between and within subjects? This paper attempts to instigate an answer to this question, regarding products within a pre-purchase context, by applying theories of psychology that focus on the role of the stimuli in emotion eliciting processes.

Context of product emotions

Psychology has not -yet- established neither a theory nor a definition of emotion that is univocally accepted (e.g., Ackerman 1990, Davidson and Cacioppo 1992). What is accepted however, is the notion that emotions are compounded phenomena involving expressive, behavioural, experiential, and physiological facets (e.g. Ortony, Clore and Collins, 1988). All emotions include responses regarding one or more of these facets. For example, a person who is pleasantly surprised when spotting a new mobile telephone, could display a surprised facial expression, act in an overt approaching manner, experience a feeling of surprise, and have a risen heart rate. Although important questions can be asked about all of these four facets, for the current purposes these facets are not relevant, but rather the eliciting conditions that preceded them. Consequently, our question is not "how can this person's surprise be defined?" but rather "why is this person surprised?". In other words, we are interested in finding the specific factor that is responsible for this subject's emotion in the product-subject interaction. A logical first step is to define what response can be labelled as 'surprise'. For this, a measurement instrument is required that measures the emotional responses to products. A difficulty in finding a suitable measurement instrument is that the number of possible emotional responses to products seems unlimited. However, this paper only considers emotions elicited by products in a pre-purchase context. Hence, an instrument that is capable of measuring emotions that can be experienced within this specific context is sufficient.

Although it could be argued that products can elicit every possible emotion, in this restricted context some emotions are more relevant than others. Pride for example, will not be experienced in a pre-purchase context because one can only be proud of a product if one owns it. Emotions such as surprise and boredom on the other hand, can very well be experienced within this context.

An empirical study was conducted to find which of the emotions are most prevalent within the considered context (Desmet and Hekkert 1999). A set of 18 emotions that occur most frequently came out of this study. Table 1 shows this set.

As this paper focuses on the photostudy, readers interested in PrEmo are referred to Desmet, Hekkert and Jacobs (1999) which reports the development and an application of PrEmo.

The set was used as a basis for developing a measurement instrument to measure the 18 possible emotional responses to product design: Product motion measure (PrEmo). The non-verbal self-report instrument is based on the set of emotions depicted in table 1. These emotions are visualised by animations of a cartoon character and presented on a computer interface. Subjects can express themselves by selecting those animations that correspond with their felt emotion. Figure 1 shows the interface of PrEmo.

Positive emotions	Negative emotions
Enthusiastic	Disgusted
Inspired	Indignant
Desiring	Aversive
Attracted to	Disappointed
Fascinated	Bored
Softened	Disillusioned
Satisfied	Vulnerable
Appreciative	Contemptuous
Pleasantly surprised	Dissatisfied

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Table 1 Set of pre-purchase product emotions

Functional view on emotions

A functional approach is most suited for an inquiry into mixed product emotions because it focuses especially on the meaning of the stimulus that elicits the emotion. Therefore, this approach is discussed in the current paper.

Emotions are seen to be functional in the sense that they regulate behaviour in a manner that is beneficial for the individual. They will pull us towards 'good' stimuli and push us away from 'bad' stimuli (Arnold 1960). Events are signalled as emotionally relevant (good or bad) when they appear to favour or harm one or more of the individual's 'concerns'. These concerns are more or less stable preferences for certain states of the world; they are our personal motives in

Figure 1 The PrEmo interface

life (Frijda 1988). Examples of human concerns are concerns for respect, safety, self-esteem, etcetera. For instance, we all have the concern of being treated with the respect we believe we deserve. When a person receives a degrading comment from a colleague, he will probably find this event conflicting with this concern for respect. Consequently this person will experience a negative emotion such as shame or anger.

The preceding example illustrates that the linking of the stimulus to the concerns precedes the actual emotional response. This process of 'signalling the emotional relevancy of an event' is most commonly conceptualised as 'a process of appraisal' (e.g.,

Arnold 1960, Frijda 1986, Ortony, Clore, & Collins 1988). Appraisal theories assert that it is not events per se that determine emotional responses, but evaluations and interpretations of events. When we look at our example of the person who receives a degrading comment, the conceptualisation of appraisal might offer us possible alternative emotional responses. It might be that in this specific situation the person does not appraise the insult as a lack of respect but rather as a witty form of humour. In that case the person could experience a positive emotion, such as joy.

Hence, the theory of appraisal can be useful to understanding why emotions differ between individuals. Whereas two individuals with different appraisals of the same stimulus will respond with different emotions, they will respond with the same emotions if they have the same appraisals (Frijda 1986). The next section demonstrates how this proposition can be applied to the set of 18 possible product emotions.

Emotional concerns regarding products

To obtain insight in what emotional concerns people have regarding products, an explorative study was conducted. In this study, 25 subjects were asked to photograph products from their surroundings, that elicit one of the 18 emotions.¹ Each subject was instructed to make ten photos and to record in a notebook what emotion each photographed product elicits and why it elicits this specific emotion. The study resulted in a set of some 250 photos of products and a database. The database shows -for each photo- what emotion was experienced and why it was experienced.

The set combined with the database provides a vast anecdotal overview of eliciting conditions of (the set of 18) product emotions. Figure 2 shows an example of a product that elicited a desiring response and a product that elicited an aversive response.

Product: Boot

Emotional response: desiring

Comment of the subject:

I picture myself wearing this boot. I'll look elegant, confident, feminine, and seductive. I desire for this moment when I observe the boot.

Product: Sellotape dispenser

Emotional response: Aversive

Comment of the subject:

It won't work because it is too light, both the teeth and the tape appear to be of bad quality.

Figure 2 Two examples of products that elicit emotions

¹ The subjects were either professional designers or researchers in the field of product design. This was decided because the task was expected to be not an easy one. As the chosen subjects were -because of their profession- used to be conscious of the products that surround them, it was presumed that they would be able to execute the task properly.

Based on the remarks the subjects noted in their logbook, an assumption was made of what the subjects' concerns could have been with

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which the products either corresponded or collided.² The concern the boot in figure 1 corresponds with, appears to be of a social nature: A concern of ‘social interaction’. The concern the tape dispenser collides with, appears to be of a functional nature: A concern of ‘using tape in an efficient and user-friendly way’. As expected, the self-reports of the total set revealed a seemingly unlimited number of possible concerns, including social, aesthetic, and functional ones. Therefore, the relevancy of the concerns appears to be limited unless some sort of structure can be imposed on them.

Some scholars attempt to structure the limitless number of emotional concerns (e.g., Roseman 1991, Scherer 1994). A structure, which might be of value in understanding the mixed character of emotional responses to products, is the well accepted one developed by Ortony, Clore and Collins (1988). This structure (the OCC structure) distinguishes three basic types of concerns: (1) Goals, (2) standards, and (3) attitudes. First, goals are the things one wants to see happen (e.g., I want to publish a book). Second, standards are the things one believes ought to happen (e.g., I shouldn’t disrespect my parents). And third, attitudes are one’s dispositional likings or dislikings such as tastes (e.g., I love cheesecake). This theory implies that a stimulus can elicit three types of emotions, depending on which concern type is focused.

This implication is illustrated with the following example: After telling his mummy that he is hungry, a little boy is granted with an apple. If the boy focuses on his goal, he might feel relief because finally he gets something to stop his hunger. On the other hand, if he focuses on his standards, he might be indignant because he believes he is entitled to something tastier like a chocolate bar. Finally, if he focuses on his attitudes, he might experience an aversive response because he doesn’t like the taste of apples. In reality these emotional responses will probably occur simultaneously. In other words, the boy will experience mixed emotions.

The OCC structure proves to be useful in categorising the large quantity of concerns that was found in the photostudy. The emotional concerns regarding the photoset cover all three of the basic types: Some of the products on the photos elicit emotions because they collide or correspond with goals, others

with standards, and others with attitudes. Figure 3, 4, and 5 show examples of products which elicit emotions because of these three concerns respectively.

The Kangaroo ball elicits enthusiasm because the subject anticipates the joy and fun it would provide when she would use it. Hence, it corresponds with her goal (how she would like it to be) to play and have fun.

² One could correctly assert that our proposals of emotional concerns are based on subjective interpretations of the self-reports.

However, the end goal of this paper is not to propose possible concerns but to propose an explanation for occurring mixed emotions. Therefore, the subjective interpretations are justified with the claim that they are for illustrative purposes only.

figure 3 Kangaroo ball: Goals

Product: Kangaroo ball

Emotional response:
Enthusiasm

Comment of the subject:
The thought of playing with the Kangaroo ball makes me enthusiastic.

Figure 4 New Beetle: Standards

Product: New Beetle

Emotional response: disappointed

Comment of the subject:

I think this car is superfluous.

The form is predictable and it is cheap trick of Volkswagen to try and benefit from an old success.

This subject believes it is not appropriate of Volkswagen to reintroduce a million selling car-concept in the hope to repeat the success by appealing to the nostalgic feelings of consumers. Hence, the car collides with his standard (how he believes it should be) of design integrity.

The subject is attracted simply by the aesthetics of this object. The shoehorn corresponds with his attitude (his dispositional likings) of aesthetic taste.

Product: Shoehorn

Emotional response: Attracted to

Comment of the subject:

Nice red color, sober formgiving.

Figure 5 Shoehorn: Attitudes

The three different kinds of concerns that can be addressed by products offer an explanation of the variations in emotional responses both between and within subjects. Between subjects, a product can elicit different emotions because of two reasons. First, the subjects can focus on different concerns (e.g., whereas one subject might experience indignation because the New Beetle collides with a standard-type concern, another subject might experience attraction because it corresponds a goal-type concern). Second, the subjects can differ in their concerns (e.g., they can have different attitude-type concerns such as tastes).

The OCC structure elucidates the fact that one stimulus can elicit independent emotions simultaneously by distinguishing three concern types. The photostudy showed that all three types can be addressed by consumer products. Hence, we conclude that within subjects, products can elicit mixed (and possibly conflicting) emotions because in those cases they simultaneously address different types of concerns.

Future research

The results of the photostudy will be studied more extensively in order to find relationships between product design and emotional responses. Furthermore, this relationship will be studied in experiments with the PrEmo instrument. It is our goal to use knowledge of this relationships for the development of a new set of tools that will support designers to evaluate and influence the emotional impact of their designs.

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